

Rediscovery of *Ceropegia maculata* Bedd. (Apocynaceae: Ceropegieae) after 154 years from Tamil Nadu, India

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Abstract

Ceropegia maculata Bedd. has been rediscovered after a period of 154 years from Tamil Nadu. A detailed description and other relevant information are provided based on recent collections. A key to the species of section *Janthina* Huber in Western Ghats is also provided.

The genus *Ceropegia* L. (Asclepiadoideae; Ceropegieae) is commonly known as lantern flowers (Chavan et al., 2018) and flytrap flowers (Masinde, 2004). It is the largest genus in the tribe *Ceropegieae* and represented by 383 species (POWO, 2018) with the main centre of diversity in Africa. Karthikeyan et al. (2009) have enumerated 56 species, 2 subspecies and 3 varieties from India. Since then few more taxa have been described by different authors from various parts of India: *Ceropegia attenuata* Hook. var. *mookambikae* (Diwakar & Singh, 2011), *C. bhatii* (Yadav & Shendage, 2010), *C. concanensis* (Kambale et al., 2012), *C. mahabalei* Hemadri & Ansari var. *hemalatae* (Rahangdale & Rahangdale, 2012), *C. karulensis* (Punekar et al., 2013), *C. maharashtrensis* (Punekar et al., 2013), *C. manoharii* (Sujanapal et al., 2013), *C. mizoramensis* (Kumar et al., 2018), *C. murlensis* (Kumar et al., 2018), *C. nampanyana* (Manudev et al., 2016), *C. pullaiihii* (Kullayiswamy et al., 2012) and *C. ravikumariana* (Kambale & Gnanasekaran, 2016). Despite their great variation in shape, size, ornamentation, color and color patterns, most *Ceropegia* species can be easily recognized immediately in the field by the cage-like apex formed by the convergence of the five corolla lobe tips (Kidyoo, 2015a, b). Nayar et al. (2014) have reported 46 taxa of *Ceropegia* from the Western Ghats, among them 37 species and 2 varieties are endemic (Kambale & Yadav, 2013; Singh et al., 2015). The level of endemism suggests the Western Ghats as one of the centres for evolution and diversification of *Ceropegia* (Singh et al., 2015). It is known from earlier studies that 21 species and 2 varieties are found in Tamil Nadu (Srinivasan, 1987; Kambale & Gnanasekaran, 2016; Swarupanandan & Mangaly, 1992; Umamaheswari & Daniel, 2001) of these *Ceropegia mannarana*, *C. omissa*, *C. ravikumariana* and *C. schumanniana* are strict endemics.

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During the systematic study of the Asclepiadoideae of Tamil Nadu, the authors have collected some interesting specimens of *Ceropegia* from the Dry evergreen forests of Tirunelveli Hills, Southern Western Ghats. Critical studies with pertinent literature ([Ansari, 1984](#); [Jagtap & Singh, 1999](#)) it is identified as *Ceropegia maculata*. This little-known asclepiad belongs to the section *Janthina* due to the presence of a ring of hairs at the top of the dilated base and in the undivided erect inner coronal lobes ([Huber, 1957](#)). So far six species viz., *C. decaisneana* Wight, *C. thwaitesii* Hook., *C. elegans* Wall., *C. maculata* Bedd., *C. manoharii* Sujanapal et al. and *C. schumanniana* Swarupan. & Mangaly have been reported in the sec. *Janthina* Huber from Western Ghats ([Nayar et al., 2014](#)). *Ceropegia maculata* was first described by R. H. Beddome, based on the collection made from Anamalai Hills, Tamil Nadu ([Beddome, 1864](#)). Later it was recollected by C. A. Barber from Naduvengad, Travancore in 1905. Since then, there seems to be no record of its collection in India hence, [Ansari \(1988\)](#) designated the species as possibly extinct. However, [Sasidharan & Swarupanandan \(1994\)](#) rediscovered and reported it from Sholayar forests, Kerala. Furthermore, hitherto there was no report on the occurrence of the species either from the type locality ([Kambale, 2015](#); [Subbaiyan et al., 2015](#)) or other parts of Tamil Nadu ([Krishnamurthy et al., 2014](#); [Srinivasan, 1987](#); [Matthew, 1995, 1999](#); [Sankar et al., 2012](#)). Hence, the present collection of this species from Tirunelveli Hills, Tamil Nadu after an elapse of more than 150 years not only a rediscovery but also extends the known distribution range further south in Western Ghats. Therefore, it deserves phytogeographical significance. Since the species is known only by very few old collections at Madras Herbarium (MH) and Central National Herbarium (CAL), a detailed description, photo plate ([Figure 1](#)) and pertinent notes are provided here for easy identification and better understanding of species.

Key to the species of section *Janthina* Huber in Western Ghats

- | | |
|--|------------------------|
| 1a. Leaves and peduncles glabrous..... | 2 |
| 1b. leaves or peduncles or both hairy..... | <i>C. decaisneana</i> |
| 2a. Mouth of the corolla tube funnel-shaped; outer coronal lobes deltoid, hairy..... | 3 |
| 2b. Mouth of the corolla tube narrow; outer coronal lobes narrow, glabrous..... | 5 |
| 3a. Outer and inner corona equal in size..... | <i>C. elegans</i> |
| 3b. Outer corona shorter than inner corona..... | 4 |
| 4a. Corolla tube funnel shaped at throat..... | <i>C. thwaitesii</i> |
| 4b. Corolla tube sub-cylindric to slightly dilated at throat..... | <i>C. manoharii</i> |
| 5a. Peduncles 2-3 cm long; outer coronal scales taller than the gynostegium,
hairy at base..... | <i>C. maculata</i> |
| 5b. Peduncles 2-3 cm long; outer coronal scales as long as the gynostegium,
glabrous at base..... | <i>C. schumanniana</i> |

Figure 1. *Ceropegia maculata*.

a) Habit; b) stem; c) leaves; d) inflorescence; e) young flower; f) flower; g) close-up view of corolla with hairs.

Taxonomic Treatment

Ceropegia maculata Bedd. in Madras J. Lit. Sci. Ser. 3 (1): 52. 1864; Gamble, Fl. Madras 4: 859. 1921; Huber in Mem. Soc. Brot. 12: 176. 1957; Ansari, Fasc. Fl. India 16: 23. 1984; S. R. Sriniv. in Henry & al., Fl. Tamil Nadu Ind., Ser I: Analysis 2: 84. 1987; Ansari in M. P. Nayar & Sastry, Red Data Book Indian Pl. 2: 46. 1988; Sasidh. & Swarup. in J. Econ. Taxon. Bot. 18: 631. 1994; A. P. Jagtap & N. P. Singh, Fasc. Fl. India 24: 223. 1999; T. S. Nayar & al., Fl. Pl. Kerala: 86. 2006; Karthik. & al., Fl. Pl. India 1: 162. 2009. **Lectotype** (designated by [Kambale & Yadav, 2014](#)): INDIA. Tamil Nadu; Anaimalais (Anamallays), *Beddome s.n.* (CAL, CAL0000018018).

Twiners; stems terete with prominent spots. Leaves simple, opposite-decussate; petiole 1.5 – 3.5 cm long, channeled above, pilose along margin; lamina ovate - lanceolate, 5–9.5 x 1.5–5 cm, acute - acuminate at apex, narrow at the base, with glands at the base of lamina, punctate, glabrous above, ciliate along nerves beneath and along margin. Flowers in extra-axillary, 3–5-flowered umbellate cymes; peduncle 1.4–2.5 cm long, slender, glabrous; pedicels up to 2 cm long. Calyx 5-partite, sepals linear-subulate, 2–5 mm long, glabrous. Corolla 2 cm long, pale greenish-purple; corolla tube 1–1.5 cm long, curved, dilated at the base, ring of hairs at the throat within; corolla lobes oblong or oblong-lanceolate, 3–5 mm long, green or bluish-green, hairy, connate at tip forming ovoid cage. Corona biseriate; outer corona of 5 deeply bifid lobes, connate at the tip, as long as inner corona, hairy at the base; inner corona of 5 erect processes, alternate with outer corona. Pollinarium erect, 0.4 x 0.4 mm; pollinia reddish-yellow with pellucid margin, globose, attached to brown corpusculum by short caudicles. Fruit setting rare, follicles 10–20 cm long, terete, thin.

Flowering & Fruiting: June – February.

Distribution: INDIA (Kerala and Tamil Nadu), Endemic ([Kambale and Yadav, 2015](#)).

Specimens examined: INDIA: Kerala; Thrissur district, Sholayar forest, 19 Sep 1983, 600 m, *N. Sasidharan* 2954 (KFRI, acc. no. 4241imgae!); Travancore district, Naduvengad, 29 Nov 1905, *C. A. Barber* 7166 (MH!). Tamil Nadu; Tirunelveli Dist., Karaiyar dam to Inchikuzhi on way to Kouthalai from 750 m asl, 22.07.2016, *C. Rajasekar et al.* 500 (BUH!); same place, 680 m asl., 22.02.2017, *C. Rajasekar et al.* 1572 (BUH!)

Habitat: This climber is occasionally seen in the Dry evergreen forests at 600-800 m altitude. The following species viz., *Aristolochia krisagathra*, *Begonia malabarica*, *B. floccifera*, *Capparis diversifolia*, *C. rheedii*, *Ceropegia candelabrum*, *Ceropegia elegans*, *Croton caudatus*, *Cymbidium ensifolium*, *Habenaria multicudata*, *Helicteres isora*, *Hydnocarpus alpina*, *Mallotus*

philippensis, *Memecylon subcordatum*, *Pavetta oblanceolata* and *Thunbergia fragrans* are commonly found in the locality.

Note: The species of *Ceropegia* in India are under threat mainly because of destructive collection and habitat degradation (Ramamurthy et al., 2012). Most of the endemic species of *Ceropegia* are being restricted only to a special habitat and need narrow ecological niche for its survival and merit special consideration in their conservation (Yadav, 1996). In order to evolve long term conservation strategies, it is critical to collate information on their distribution, present status and immediate threats (Yadav & Kamble, 2008).

Conservation Status: Currently we do not know the exact population size and extent of occurrence of the species in Western Ghats; hence we have assigned the threat status as Data Deficient (DD).

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